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**About Very Perfect
Numbers**

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About Very Perfect Numbers¹

A natural number n is named very perfect if $\sigma(\sigma(n))=2n$ (see [1]).

Theorem. The square of an odd prime number can't be very perfect number.

Proof. Let be $n=p^2$, where p is an odd prime number, then $\sigma(n)=1+p+p^2$, $\sigma(\sigma(n))=\sigma(1+p+p^2)=2p^2$. We decompose $\sigma(n)$ in canonical form, from where $1+p+p^2=p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_k^{\alpha_k}$. Because $p(p+1)+1$ is odd, in the canonical decompose must be only odd primes.

$$\sigma(\sigma(n)) = (1+p_1^{\alpha_1} + \dots + p_1^{\alpha_1 \alpha_1}) \dots (1+p_k^{\alpha_k} + \dots + p_k^{\alpha_k \alpha_k}) = \frac{p_1^{\alpha_1+1} - 1}{p_1 - 1} \dots \frac{p_k^{\alpha_k+1} - 1}{p_k - 1} = 2p^2.$$

Because $\frac{p_i^{\alpha_i+1} - 1}{p_i - 1} > 2, \dots, \frac{p_k^{\alpha_k+1} - 1}{p_k - 1} > 2,$

one gets that $2p^2$ can't be decomposed in more than two factors, so each one > 2 , therefore $k \leq 2$.

Case 1. For $k = 1$ we find $\sigma(n) = 1 + p + p^2 = p_1^{\alpha_1}$, from where one gets $p_1^{\alpha_1-1} = p_1(1+p+p^2)$ and

$$\sigma(\sigma(n)) = \frac{p_1^{\alpha_1+1} - 1}{p_1 - 1} = 2p^2,$$

$p_1(1+p+p^2)-1=2p^2(p_1-1)$, from where $p_1-1 = p(pp_1-2p-p_1)$. The right side is divisible by p , thus p_1-1 is a p multiple. Because $p_1 > 2$ it results $p_1 \geq p-1$ and

$p_1^2 \geq (p-1)^2 > p^2+p+1 = p_1^{\alpha_1}$,
 thus $\alpha_1 = 1$ and $\sigma(n) = p^2+p-1 = p_1$, $\sigma(\sigma(n)) = \sigma(p_1) = 1 + p_1$. If n is very perfect then $1 + p_1 = 2p^2$ or $p^2+p+2 = 2p^2$. The solutions of the equation are $p = -1$ and $p = 2$ which is a contradiction.

Case 2. For $k=2$ we have $\sigma(n)=p^2+p+1 = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2}$.

$$\sigma(\sigma(n)) = (1+p_1^{\alpha_1} + \dots + p_1^{\alpha_1 \alpha_1})(1+p_2^{\alpha_2} + \dots + p_2^{\alpha_2 \alpha_2}) = \frac{p_1^{\alpha_1+1} - 1}{p_1 - 1} \cdot \frac{p_2^{\alpha_2+1} - 1}{p_2 - 1} = 2p^2.$$

Because $\frac{p_1^{\alpha_1+1} - 1}{p_1 - 1} > 2$ and $\frac{p_2^{\alpha_2+1} - 1}{p_2 - 1} > 2$

it results

$$\frac{p_1^{\alpha_1+1} - 1}{p_1 - 1} = p \text{ and } \frac{p_2^{\alpha_2+1} - 1}{p_2 - 1} = 2p$$

(or inverse),

thus $p_1^{\alpha_1+1} - 1 = p(p_1 - 1)$, $p_2^{\alpha_2+1} - 1 = 2p(p_2 - 1)$,

then

$$p_1^{\alpha_1+1} p_2^{\alpha_2+1} - p_1^{\alpha_1+1} - p_2^{\alpha_2+1} + 1 = 2p^2 (p_1 - 1) (p_2 - 1),$$

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thus $\sigma(n) = p^2 + p + 1 = p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1} p_2^{\alpha_2 - 1}$

and $p_1 p_2 (p^2 + p + 1) = 2p^2(p_1 - 1)(p_2 - 1) + p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1} + p_2^{\alpha_2 - 1} - 1$

or $p_1 p_2 p(p+1) + p_1 p_2 - 1 = 2p^2(p_1 - 1)(p_2 - 1) + (p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1} - 1) + (p_2^{\alpha_2 - 1} - 1) = 2p^2(p_1 - 1)(p_2 - 1) + p(p_1 - 1) + 2p(p_2 - 1)$ accordingly p divides $p_1 p_2 - 1$, thus $p_1 p_2 > p + 1$ and $p_1^2 p_2^2 \geq (p + 1)^2 > p^2 + p + 1 = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2}$. Hence:

Π_1) If $\alpha_1 = 1$ and $n = 2p^2$, then $\sigma(n) = p^2 + p + 1 = p_1 p_2^{\alpha_2}$

$$\text{and } \frac{p_1^2 - 1}{p_1 - 1} = p \text{ and } \frac{p_2^{\alpha_2 + 1} - 1}{p_2 - 1} = 2p,$$

thus $p_1 + 1 = p$ which is a contradiction.

Π_2) If $\alpha_2 = 1$ and $n = 2p^2$, then $\sigma(n) = p^2 + p + 1 = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2$

$$\text{and } \frac{p_1^{\alpha_1 - 1} - 1}{p_1 - 1} = p \text{ and } \frac{p_2^2 - 1}{p_2 - 1} = 2p,$$

thus $p_2 + 1 = 2p$, $p_2 = 2p - 1$ and $\sigma(n) = p^2 + p + 1 = p_1^{\alpha_1} (2p + 1)$,

from where $4\sigma(n) = (2p - 1)(2p + 3) + 7 = 4p^2 + 4p - 1$, accordingly 7 is divisible by $2p - 1$ and thus p is divisible by 4 which is a contradiction.

Reference :

I Suryanarayana, Elemente der Mathematik, 1969.

[“Octogon”, Braşov, Vol. 5, No. 2, 53-4, October 1997.]